

EFFECT OF COACHING PROGRAM ON NURSE MANAGERS' INTERPERSONAL SKILLS AND NURSES' MOTIVATION

FATMA ESSAM*

PhD Researcher, Faculty of Nursing, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt.
*Corresponding Author Email: 11222018569698@pg.cu.edu.eg

NEHAD E. FEKRY

Professor Doctor, Department of Nursing Administration, Faculty of Nursing, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt.
Email: Nehad_fekry@hotmail.com

SAHAR HASSAN

Professor Doctor, Department of Nursing Administration, Faculty of Nursing, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt.
Email: sherif.tours@yahoo.com

Abstract

Background; Organizations are under obligation to respond wisely and creatively to the challenges of the modern workplace due to its fast pace, frequent and disruptive change, and complexity. Furthermore, there is a growing demand for manager-led coaching worldwide since it is considered one of the most powerful development activities, cost-efficient, and successful than hiring an external coach. Recently, nurse managers mastering coaching and interpersonal skills considered an advantage for prestigious health organizations. This paper aimed to examine the effect of coaching on nurse managers' interpersonal skills and nurses' motivation. **Methods:** A quasi-experimental design was utilized. The study was conducted from July 2021 to March 2022, at a private hospital in Cairo, consists of eight floors, 300 bed capacity, covered with different medical specialties and units. Convenient sample of (36) nurse managers' and (154) staff nurses were participated in this study. Four tools were utilized; "Nurse Manager interpersonal skills observational checklist, 'coaching observational checklist, Nurses' motivation questionnaire, and Nurse Managers' coaching knowledge test". **Results:** a statistically significant increase in total observed interpersonal skills mean scores during different periods of observation ($f=166.800$; $p=.0001^*$), a significant increase in total observed coaching skills mean scores between rehearsal and execution ($t=9.153$; $p=.0001^*$), a statistically significant increase in mean scores of nurses' motivation between pre & post assessment ($t=26.94$; $p=.0001^*$), and a significant increase in mean scores of nurse managers' coaching knowledge was observed between the pre- and post-program implementation ($t=30.6$; $p=.0001^*$). Additionally, a high statistically significant correlation was identified between coaching skills dimensions and observed interpersonal skills, during different periods of observation ($R=0.71$, $P=.0001^*$). **Conclusion:** Implementation of the coaching training program for nurse managers has been demonstrated to have a positive effect on nurse managers' coaching knowledge, coaching and interpersonal skills, and staff nurses' motivation levels in the clinical settings.

Keywords: Coaching – Nurse Managers – Interpersonal Skills – Nurses' Motivation.

BACKGROUND

Coaching is becoming more and more commonplace globally in both academics and businesses, it has evolved into a managerial discipline with an effect on staff development and organizational performance. (McCarthy and Milner, 2020). According to the International Coaching Federation (ICF) (2020), the number of individuals working as coaching professionals worldwide surpassed 71,000 in 2019. While, by the ICF projections the global investment in workplace coaching exceeds two billion US dollars

annually. Indeed, the prevalence of coaching in the workplace has led to a notable trend of businesses offering it to their most valued employees as a form of incentive. (ICF, 2020).

Coaching is an intervention or component of a complex intervention for leadership development among healthcare managers, including but not limited to leadership knowledge, behaviors, skills, attitudes, and practices (Westcott, 2016 and Hastings; Kane .2018). The specific skills that managers seem to need include the ability to coach a team, conduct a contract, provide feedback, and build rapport with participants. In addition, the ability to coach in a manner that makes the coached staff aware that coaching is taking place considered as a crucial skill. (Lawrence 2017).

The staff members who participate in coaching programs have the opportunity to receive inspiration, motivation, and encouragement to advance in their professional careers. This, in turn, contributes to the organization's financial sustainability. The coaching process is characterized as a straightforward, communicative in nature, mutually beneficial, and confidential process where the coach and the coached staff works together to accomplish both personal and professional objectives. (Rothwell & Bakhshandeh.2022).

In the professional setting, managerial coaching has been identified as a remarkably efficacious developmental strategy. Despite the existence of numerous coaching methodologies, the management coaching approach has emerged as a particularly prominent one, experiencing a notable surge in popularity. Managerial coaching is when a leader acting as a coach or facilitator of learning, executing particular behaviors that promote the growth and development of their staff, and enhance their performance. (Lawrence, 2017; Ellinger et al., 2023; Bozer & Delegach.2019). The long-term success of coaching is significantly impacted by the coach's style during the coaching session and throughout the coaching interpersonal relationship. Research indicates that coaches who are able to modify their approach to align with the preferences and fundamental coaching style of those they coach typically have more efficient coaching relationships. (MacLennan. 2017; Blanton & Wasylyshyn. 2018)

Interpersonal skills have been identified as indicators of long-term work performance in healthcare contexts. These skills are linked to staff perspectives and outcomes at both personal and team level, as well as productivity at the organizational level. Moreover, interpersonal skills are in great demand for both managerial performance and organizational success (Beenen et al. 2018; Rios et al. 2020). Skills like listening, contracting and expressing curiosity through propping questions, clarification or exploring details, proper action to be taken and process review are all used by nurse managers as a coaching skills facilitating interpersonal relation. In order to develop interpersonal skills, it is essential to employ active listening, which is defined as a combination of verbal and nonverbal abilities. Active listening techniques include head nodding, maintaining eye contact, reiterating essential details, establishing goals and providing feedback to the staff being coached, which can assist them in acquiring self-assurance, creativity, and confidence in their own decision-making abilities. (Westcott.2016; Burrows.2018).

Motivation in leadership is defined as a stable mind, spirit, desire, strength, or driving force of interest within the individual, which is subsequently manifested in action. This notion encompasses the synergy of various stimuli that influence the behavior of staff members in the context of their work performance (Marquis & Huston, Jones, 2018). Furthermore, motivation has been demonstrated to have a significant impact on job satisfaction and performance. The relationship between low employee motivation and both low job satisfaction and inadequate performance cannot be separated as the staff require ongoing motivation, encouragement, and support to function, relate, and progress (Matteson et al.2021; and Mear & Werner, 2020).

The coaching and interpersonal relations are great approaches to motivate and engage staff members as well as support managers in the workplace. (Susanto & Sawitri. 2022; Susanto, et al. 2023a; Susanto, et al. 2023b). In point of fact, coaching was regarded as an organizational management approach more than 70 years prior to the present. In recent years, the majority of research on organizational coaching has centered on managers receiving coaching to enhance their personal capabilities and promote organizational improvement. Consequently, today's nurses require leaders that helps them to identify innovative manners to address challenges and get better results, support them to acquire new skills and solve challenges on their own. (Lundin, et al.,2022; and Backman, et al., 2020).

A review of some prior studies supports the clinical experience of the researcher in the study setting, as it was observed that staff nurses are missing the motive to work, as they was facing a multiple work pressures, over workloads, responsibility and burnout, with no opportunities to be listened, they were missing the interpersonal relations with their managers and pushed to achieve only organizational goals without any considerations to their personal goals, that was mainly because of leaders' management styles and interrupted interpersonal skills. (Al-Yami et al 2018). Therefore, the findings of this study may benefit leaders of the healthcare sectors, as managing by coaching could directly affect the "manager & staff" "relations, motivation, goals attainment, satisfaction, morals, engagement, and maintaining retention and productivity", that's why, the hospital nurse managers and top leaders expressed a keen interest in participating in the coaching program to improve both coaching skills, interpersonal skills, and in turn promotes much better staff motivation.

The aim of this study was to examine the effect of coaching program on nurse managers' interpersonal skills and nurses' motivation. To fulfill this, aim the following hypotheses was formulated: **H1**. After implementation of the coaching program there will be a difference in nurse manager's score of the interpersonal skills, compared to pre-program, and also to follow up score. **H2**. After implementation of the coaching program there will be a difference in nurse manager's coaching knowledge test scores, compared to pre-program. **H3**. Staff nurses' motivation level score will be affected after implementation of the coaching program compared to preprogram.

Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework for this study depends on merging the Hawkins' P. model (CLEAR coaching model) with Imogene King's theory (Goal Attainment theory).

The CLEAR Coaching Model was developed in the early 1980s by Peter Hawkins and provided a process framework that clarifies what is needed by the individual being coached and a structured approach to arrive at needed actions, Initially, the model was developed as a supervision model and subsequently applied to individual coaching. (Hawkins &Smith, 2013).

The model has 5 phases, "CLEAR" stands for: Contracting, Listening, Exploring, Action, Review

- **Contracting** refers to the initiation of the coaching session, wherein the coach commences the discussion and delineates the topics to be covered, establish the set of guidelines/ rules through consultation with the client. This stage is pivotal in determining the mutual expectations and objectives of the client and the coach, as it serves as the foundation for subsequent coaching activities.
- **Listening;** The stage when the coach pays meticulous attention to the words and body language of the client to ascertain the nature of the client's communication. The coach may also pose inquiries or proffer alternative lines of thought that facilitate client acquisition of valuable insights regarding the issues being discussed.
- **Exploring;** it's a two-part process. Firstly, it entails the client working towards understanding their own personal impact of the situation. Secondly, it involves the exploration of potential future actions to reach a satisfactory resolution of the situation.
- **Action;** In this phase, the coach assists the client in selecting the appropriate course of action and in formulating the steps that the client will take over the course of time.
- **Review;** This phase encompasses the summary of the points that were covered in the coaching session and the highlighting of the decisions that the client has made. The coach also gathers feedback from the client regarding the helpfulness of the session and the aspects that should be modified during future sessions.

Imogene King's Theory of Goal Attainment was first introduced in the 1960s. From the title itself, the model focuses on the attainment of certain goals. It explains the symbiotic nature of partnership, emphasizing the reciprocal exchange of information, collaborative goal setting, and concerted efforts to achieve objectives. (King, 1971).

There are three interacting systems in the Theory of Goal Attainment according to King. These are the personal system, the interpersonal system, and the social system/ goal attainments.

By merging the CLEAR coaching model with goal attainment theory, nurse managers and staff nurses interact with one another and stay encouraged and motivated to promote a change in their perspective., both in terms of their own capabilities and the manner in which they interpret situations and interact with others.

This interaction is crucial because it serves as a catalyst for a transformative shift, which is a prerequisite for the success of any professional coaching session.

METHODS

Research Design:

A quasi-experimental design with one group pretest-posttest was utilized to achieve the aim of the current study. Quasi-experimental research design is an empirical study used to estimate the causal impact of an intervention on its target population without random assignment to treatment or control, and it is generally somewhere between correlational studies and true experiments (Siedlecki, 2020).

Setting:

This study was executed at a private hospital in Cairo, the hospital had 300 beds, it consisted of eight main floors covered with different medical specialties and units (medical surgical, orthopedics, maternal and obstetric, intensive care units, emergency department, oncology, spinal surgery, and renal transplants. Cath-lab unit, renal dialysis and outpatient clinics.

Sample:

First sample: A convenience Sample of all the nurse managers working at the time of data collection (supervisors, head nurses and charge nurses' / team leader), was included in the sample. They were (36) nurse manager

Second sample: A convenience Sample of all the staff nurses working at the time of data collection was included in the sample. They were (154) staff nurse.

Data collection Tools

The data collection measures implemented in this study spanned from July 2021 to March 2022. During this period, four tools were utilized for data collection. These tools were developed by the researcher following an extensive review of the existing literature (McLean et al 2005; Blessing White 2009; McCarthy & Milner 2013; de Haan et al. 2013; Kalkavan. & Katrinli.2014; de Haan et al 2016). The content validity of the instruments was established by "three field experts, academic professors and health care professionals" the acceptable scores are mentioned below.

Nurse Manager interpersonal skills observational checklist: It was divided into two parts.

1st part: Personal characteristics data sheet; it included (Age, Gender, level of education, position in the organization, years of experience in the managerial position, unit / work place and employment status).

2nd Part: Nurse Manager's interpersonal skills observational checklist, it contains 57 items, these items was grouped in three dimensions as follows; (1) Communication skills (2) Human relation skills, (3) Analytical skills. Responses was measured against 5-point

Likert scale, ranging from (1) Never (2) Rarely (3) Sometimes (4) Frequently (5) Always. The tool was utilized “pre- program, immediately one month after the program and immediately after three months post the program”. The validity of this questionnaire has been confirmed with a score of 0.9 and its reliability with Cronbach’s alpha coefficient equal to 0.83 for total scale.

Nurse Managers’ coaching observational checklist: It included observations related to monitoring coaching sessions, directed by CLEAR coaching model, it contains 21 items, these items are grouped in five dimensions as follows; (1) Contract. (2) Listen (3) Explore (4) Action & (5) Review. Responses was measured using (1) for Yes and (0) for No. The validity of this questionnaire has been confirmed with a score of 0.86 and its reliability with Cronbach’s alpha coefficient equal to 0.83 for total scale.

Nurses’ motivation questionnaire: it was a self-administered questionnaire measuring the nurses’ perceived motivation.

It had 2 parts, **1st part:** was including the personal characteristics of staff nurses, (Gender, age group, years of experience in the organization, years of experience in nursing, level of education, unit / Work place and employment status).

2nd part: was containing 31 items, these items was grouped in three dimensions, (1) Individual support and communication (2) Team spirit and collaboration, (3) Recognition and reward. Responses was measured against 5-point Likert scale ranging from (1) Never (2) Rarely (3) Sometimes (4) Frequently (5) Always.

This tool was translated into Arabic to match the different staff nurses’ level of education; tool validity was conducted. The validity of this questionnaire has been confirmed with a score of 0.9 and its reliability with Cronbach’s alpha coefficient equal to 0.83 for total scale.

Nurse Managers’ coaching knowledge test: The test was developed by the researcher as part of the training program. It consisted of 10 multiple choice questions to assess nurse managers’ knowledge regarding coaching pre and post the program.

Scoring system, the value of each question was granted one point for the correct answer and zero for the incorrect answer. The total scores for all the questions were 10 points. The validity of this questionnaire has been confirmed with a score of 0.8 and its reliability with Cronbach’s alpha coefficient equal to 0.7 for total scale.

Procedure:

Prior to data collection, formal approval was obtained from the Ethical Committee at the Faculty of Nursing, Cairo University, thereby officially approved the study. Subsequently, the Vice Dean of Higher Studies and Researches at the Faculty of Nursing, Cairo University forwarded the study's objective and significance in a detailed presentation to the general director and nursing director of the selected hospital to granted their approvals.

The study was conducted through three phases: -

Preparatory phase:

In this phase, the investigator extensively reviewed the literature relevant to coaching, interpersonal skills and motivation then developed the study tools based on revised literature, the tools validity, and reliability was measured.

A comprehensive list of nurse managers and staff nurses' names and a copy of their work schedules from the chosen working units was assembled. The researcher then explained the study's aim, nature, and significance to the participants aimed to secure their participation, then informed consent was obtained from the nurse managers and staff nurses' who agreed to participate in the study.

Nurse Managers' interpersonal skills was assessed preprogram, by the researcher using the developed observational checklist to determine the pre-program level of nurse manager's interpersonal skills. Same period the staff nurse's initial level of motivation was assessed through administration of staff motivation questionnaire. Also, the channels of communication, and the meeting times was arranged. Coaching program pre-test was administered to assess the nurse manager's level of knowledge about coaching.

Implementation phase:

After a thorough design and review, the training program was disseminated to the nurse managers. The program spanned four weeks, two sessions per week, each session takes two hours, repeatedly for another round as managers was divided into two groups for staffing and scheduling purposes. The program was structured to incorporate 16 hours of classroom instruction and practical exercises (Rehearsal), in a total of eight sessions.

Each session commenced with an introduction of the objectives and outlines and concluded with the researcher soliciting feedback, ensuring the participants was kept abreast of their progress. Furthermore, to ensure comprehension, feedback was continuously solicited after each session.

Evaluation phase:

The researcher evaluated the immediate effect of the coaching program immediately after program implementation through a real **peer coaching sessions (rehearsal)** using predesigned coaching scenarios, **then (execution)** using the coaching observational checklist to examine nurse managers acquired skills post program. Also, the Coaching knowledge test was administered to nurse managers immediately post program, to examine post program level of nurse manager's coaching knowledge.

The post-program **interpersonal skills observation checklist** was collected by investigator immediately after one month of program implementation to evaluate the participants' skills acquired from the program, two nurse managers observed daily, five days a week.

Follow up evaluation was conducted immediately at the end of the third month post-program utilized the same checklist to assess the nurse managers interpersonal skills

acquired retention and adherence to coaching practices, (T1 = baseline data collection/ immediately pre-program, T2 =Immediately after completion of one month post program, T3= Immediately after completion of 3 months post program). Staff nurses' motivation questionnaire was administered and collected by the investigator at T3. After 3 months post program.

Figure 1: Study Procedure Scheme

The Coaching educational program description:

Title:	Coaching program for nurse managers
Aim:	To provide nurse managers with necessary coaching skills to improve their coaching capabilities which directly affects their interpersonal skill, and in turn affects their staff motivation level.
Target group:	The hospital nurse managers.
Content:	The program was covered through the following educational sessions: 1. Introduction to coaching and interpersonal skills, definitions, difference between coaching and other concepts as (mentoring, counselling and psychotherapy) 2. Importance and purposes of coaching, the role & characteristics of manager as a coach. and list of coaching skills 3. Coaching skills, “continued’ Exercises on each skill. (listening, questioning, and providing feedback) 4. Coaching skills, “continued’ Exercises on (Observing & analyzing,) skills, linking coaching skills with interpersonal skills (communication, human relation and analytical). 5. Coaching process using CLEAR Model 6. Activities and rehearsal sessions on coaching process (one – to – one peer coaching session) 7. Effect of coaching on personality development and its application in the context of motivating others, then guidelines for effective coaching sessions & emphasizing strategies for successful implementation. 8. Conclusion, post program coaching observational checklist, program posttest and participant feedback
Methods of teaching:	lectures, group discussions, and activities such as actual coaching rehearsal sessions, with predesigned coaching scenarios by the investigator.
Teaching media:	Power point presentation, videos, hand out and predesigned printed coaching scenarios.
Evaluation methods	Pre and post Knowledge test Post program “Coaching observational checklist”

Statistical Analysis

Upon finalization of the data collection process, the data were scored and compiled before undergoing analysis via the “Statistical Package for the Social Sciences” (SPSS), Version 22. Parametric inferential statistics, such as descriptive statistics, frequency distribution, percentage, mean scores, and standard deviation, were utilized in the analysis. Suitable statistical tests were applied, including Pearson's correlation coefficient and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The t-test was used, and the Chi-square test was also used. Relative statistical significance tests were used to discern the relationships among the study variables. The threshold for significance was set at a p-value of less than 0.05 for all statistical analyses conducted.

RESULTS

Personal characteristics of nurse managers

As depicted in Table 1 below, among respondents the highest percentage (69.4%) of nurse managers were males, (47.2%) of them had age between 30 to less than 35 years, Additionally, (61.1%) of them were bachelor degree of nursing.

Table 1: Frequency distribution of nurse managers' personal characteristics (n=36).

Characteristics	Category	Frequency(n=36)	Percentage (%)
Age			
	20-<25	0	0.00
	25-<30	16	44.4
	30-<35	17	47.2
	35+	3	8.3
Gender			
	Male	25	69.4
	Female	11	30.6
Level of Education			
	Bachelor of nursing	22	61.1
	Master in nursing	3	8.3
	Doctorate in nursing	1	2.8
	Others	10	27.8

Work-related data of urse managers'

From the total respondents (58.3%) were charge nurses, with, (52.8%) of them had five to ten years of experience in managerial position. Additionally, all of them (100%) were working as a permanent contract, and the highest percentage (38.9%) of them were working at inpatient units.

Table 2: Frequency distribution of nurse managers' work-related data. (n=36)

Variables	Category	Frequency(n=36)	Percentage (%)
Position in organization			
	Team leader	1	2.8
	Charge nurse	21	58.3
	Head nurse	13	36.1
	Nursing supervisor	1	2.8
Years of Experience in managerial position			
	1 - less than 5 years	16	44.4
	5 - less than 10 years	19	52.8
	10 - less than 15 years	1	2.8
Employment Status			
	Permanent contract	36	100.0
	Part time	0	0.00
Working Units			
	Inpatient's units	14	38.9
	Cardiac Cath lab	3	8.3
	CCU (Coronary Care Unit)	5	13.9
	Endoscopy	1	2.8
	Emergency unit	2	5.6
	ICU (Intensive care unit)	6	16.7
	Nursing office	1	2.8
	OPD (Outpatient department)	1	2.8
	RDU (Renal Dialysis unit)	2	5.6
	x-ray (radiology department)	1	2.8

Mean differences of nurse managers interpersonal skills total dimensions as observed during different periods of assessment (pre – immediately post program implementation – and three months later.)

The study results indicated that there was a statistically significant difference in mean score regarding all dimensions of interpersonal skills, as observed during different periods of assessment, (**pre – immediately post program implementation – and three months later.**), which depicted in Table 3 as total mean scores respectively as follows (preprogram, (mean=122.3 Sd = ± 10.28), post program, (mean= 227.83 Sd= ± 8.87), follow up after 3 months of the program (mean = 237.15 Sd= ± 8.68). (F.= 166.800, P= .0001*).

Table 3: Mean differences of nurse managers interpersonal skills total dimensions (n=36)

Items	Pre		Post		Follow up		f-value	p-value
	Mean	Sd	Mean	Sd	Mean	Sd		
1. Communication skills	56.28	2.11	107.78	1.70	112.83	1.64	664.93	.0001*
a. Effective listening.	20.72	3.11	39.61	2.54	41.18	2.38	630.931	.0001*
b. Effective questioning techniques	9.89	1.12	20.00	1.26	20.94	1.30	884.866	.0001*
c. Providing instructions	15.28	2.31	28.00	1.41	29.03	1.66	617.480	.0001*
d. Providing feedback	10.39	1.89	20.14	1.57	21.68	1.22	526.429	.0001*
2. Human relations skills	43.25	4.46	79.92	2.58	82.68	2.98	145.200	.0001*
3. Analytical skills	22.78	3.74	40.17	1.50	41.65	1.82	594.166	.0001*
Total	122.31	10.28	227.83	8.87	237.15	8.68	166.800	.0001*

*Significant at p-value<0.05

Comparison between the total mean scores of nurse managers’ interpersonal skills during different periods of assessment

There was a statistically significant difference in all dimensions and totals of nurse managers’ interpersonal skills between pre & immediate post (t=42.566, p=0.000*), pre & follow up (t=46.751, p=0.000*), immediate post & follow up (t= 4.113, p=0.000*), as presented in Table (4) below.

Table 4: Comparison of total mean scores of nurse managers’ interpersonal skills during different periods of assessment (n=36).

Dimensions	Pre-post		Pre-follow up		Post-Follow up	
	T	P	t	p	T	p
1. Communication skills	104.102	0.000*	115.902	0.000*	13.790	0.000*
a. Effective listening.	25.767	0.000*	28.616	0.000*	28.616	0.000*
b. Effective questioning techniques	32.847	0.000*	35.272	0.000*	2.844	0.006*
c. Providing instructions:	25.744	0.000*	26.475	0.000*	2.590	0.012*
d. Providing feedback	21.735	0.000*	27.489	0.000*	4.242	0.000*
2. Human relations skills	38.981	0.000*	40.263	0.000*	3.835	0.000*
3. Analytical skills	23.637	0.000*	24.849	0.000*	3.437	0.001*
Total	42.566	0.000*	46.751	0.000*	4.113	0.000*

*Significant at p-value<0.05

Mean differences of nurse managers observed total coaching skills as observed during rehearsal and execution

There was a statistically significant difference of nurse managers' mean scores between rehearsal and execution regarding dimensions of (Contract ($t=4.818$, $p=.0001^*$), listen ($t=3.679$, $p=.0001^*$) & Exploring ($t=3.487$, $p=.001^*$). However, there was no statistically significant difference of nurse managers' mean scores between rehearsal and execution regarding dimensions of action ($t=0.000$, $p= 1.000$) and review ($t= 0.000$, $p= 1.000$). as presented in Table (5).

Table 5: Mean differences of nurse managers observed total coaching skills as observed during rehearsal and execution (n=36)

Items	Rehearsal		Execution		t- value	p-value
	Mean	Sd	Mean	Sd		
Contract	6.81	0.79	7.56	0.50	4.818	.0001*
Listen	5.25	0.55	5.69	0.47	3.679	.0001*
Exploring	8.94	0.67	9.47	0.61	3.487	.001*
Action	3.00	0.00	3.00	0.00	0.000	1.000
Review	2.97	0.17	2.97	0.17	0.000	1.000
Total	26.97	0.88	28.69	0.71	9.153	.0001*

*Significant at $p\text{-value}<0.05$

knowledge level of nurse managers' pre and post the coaching program implementation

There was a statistically significant increase in mean test score. The mean difference increased from (2.1) Pre -coaching program implementation to (7.5) post coaching program implementation. ($t = 30.6$ & $p = .0001^*$). As presented in table (6).

Table 6: Knowledge Test scores of nurse managers' pre and post coaching program implementation (n=36)

Items	Pre		Post		t-value	p-value
	Mean	Sd	Mean	Sd		
Test score	2.1	0.96	7.5	0.75	30.6	.0001*

*Significant at $p\text{-value}<0.05$

Frequency distribution of staff nurses' personal characteristics.

The highest percentage (55.2%) of staff nurses were male, (51.3%) were in the age group of 25-<30 years, however (61%) of them had Bachelor of nursing.

Table 7: Staff nurses' personal characteristics (n=154)

Characteristics	Category	Frequency (n)	%
Gender	Male	85	55.2
	Female	69	44.8
Age	20 - less than 25	13	8.4

	25 - to less than 30	79	51.3
	30 - to less than 35	42	27.3
	35 and above	20	13.0
Level of Education			
	Nursing diploma	21	13.6
	Nursing technical diploma	34	22.1
	Bachelor of nursing	94	61.0
	Others	5	3.2

Frequency distribution of staff nurses 'work related characteristics

There was (70.1%) of respondents had 1-<5 years' experience in organization and (36.4%) had 5-<10 years of experience in nursing, and the highest percentage of staff nurses (98.7%) were working as permanent contract. However, the highest percentage (37.7%) of staff nurses were at inpatient units. As presented in table (8).

Table 8. Frequency distribution of staff nurses 'work related characteristics (n=154)

Variables	Category	Frequency (n)	%
Years of Experience in organization			
	1 - less than 5 years	108	70.1
	5 - less than 10 years	34	22.1
	10- less than 15 years	6	3.9
	15 years and more	6	3.9
Years of Experience in nursing			
	1 - less than 5 years	35	22.7
	5 - less than 10 years	56	36.4
	10 - less than 15 years	40	26.0
	15 years and more	23	14.9
Work Status			
	Permanent contract	152	98.7
	Part time	2	1.3
Working units			
	Inpatient's units	58	37.6
	Cardiac Cath lab	7	4.5
	CCU (Coronary Care Unit)	18	11.7
	Endoscopy	3	1.9
	Emergency unit	13	8.4
	ICU (Intensive care unit)	26	16.9
	Kidney transplant unit	12	7.8
	NICU (Neonatal intensive care unit)	3	1.9
	OPD (Outpatient department)	4	2.6
	RDU (Renal Dialysis unit)	8	5.2
	x-ray (radiology department)	2	1.3

Mean difference of staff nurses' motivation total dimension during pre and post assessment.

There was a statistically significant difference between pre and post mean scores of all dimensions and the totals of staff nurses' motivation score. The total means increased

from Pre- assessment (83.44 to 128.06) to post assessment (t = 26.94 & p = .0001*). As depicted in Table 9

Table 9: Mean difference of staff nurses’ motivation total dimension during pre and post assessment. (n=154)

Items	Pre		Post		t- value	p-value
	Mean	Sd	Mean	sd		
Individual support and communication	35.39	7.66	53.92	4.02	26.59	.0001*
Team spirit and collaboration	30.84	7.72	45.68	3.36	21.85	.0001*
Recognition and reward.	17.21	4.96	28.46	2.44	25.27	.0001*
Total	83.44	18.52	128.06	8.91	26.94	.0001*

*Significant at p-value<0.05

Relationship between nurses’ motivation and their personal characteristics

There was no statistically significant correlation between total dimensions of staff nurses’ motivation and their “ age (r=0.04, p=.43) level of education (r=0.01, p=0.99), years of experience in organization (r=0.04, p=0.47) , years of experience in nursing (r=0.05, p=0.31), and gender (f=0.104, p=.74), only there was a correlation with work status (f=4.21, p=.04*) and total staff nurses motivation.

Table 10: Relationship between nurses’ motivation and their personal characteristics (n=154)

Items	R	p-value
Age	0.04	0.43
Level of Education	0.01	0.99
Years of Experience in organization	0.04	0.47
Years of Experience in nursing	0.05	0.31
Gender	F=0.104	.74
work status	F=4.21	.04*

*Significant at p-value<0.05

Correlation between nurse managers observed interpersonal skills and coaching skills.

The study revealed that there was a statistically significant strong direct Correlation between total nurse managers observed interpersonal skills and total observed coaching skills, (R = 0.71, P =.0001*)

Table 11: Correlation between nurse managers observed interpersonal skills and coaching skills.

Scores	R	p-value
Interpersonal skills and coaching skills	0.71	.0001*

*Significant at p-value<0.05

Relations between nurse managers observed interpersonal skills, coaching skills and nurses’ motivation.

The results of the study showed that the relationship between nurse manager’s coaching skills, interpersonal skills and the staff nurses’ motivation pre and post program was significantly increased in all totals, coaching skills (preprogram “mean= 26.97, SD = ± 0.88” to post-program “mean=28.69, SD = ± 0.71”), interpersonal skills (preprogram “mean= 122.31, SD = ± 10.28 to post-program “mean=227.83, SD = ± 8.87), and staff motivation (pre-Assessment “mean 83.44, SD = ± 18.52 to post-Assessment “mean=128.06, SD = ± 8.91). As showed in table (12) and figure (2).

Table 12: Correlation between nurse managers observed interpersonal skills, coaching skills and nurses’ motivation

Items	Pre		Post		t-value	p-value
	Mean	Sd	Mean	Sd		
Coaching skills	26.97	0.88	28.69	0.71	9.153	.0001*
Interpersonal Skills	122.31	10.28	227.83	8.87	42.566	0.0001*
Nurses’ Motivation	83.44	18.52	128.06	8.91	26.94	.0001*

*Significant at p-value<0.05

Figure 2: Correlation between nurse managers observed interpersonal skills, coaching skills and nurses’ motivation

DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to investigate the effect of coaching program on nurse managers’ interpersonal skills and nurses’ motivation. The findings of the study showed that, the majority of study nurse managers were in the groupage within 30–35 age range.

This finding may be attributed to the multifaceted responsibilities and demanding nature of the role of nurse managers, suggesting that this particular age group may embody a certain degree of hospital leadership wisdom in their approach to staff selection. That was consistent with a study done by Yang and Liu (2021) who found that more than half of nurse managers was at same average of age group.

The results of the current study showed that predominant proportion of study participants were male nurse managers, this may be attributable to the rising enrollment of male students in nursing education programs in Egypt, which has resulted in a male percentage exceeding fifty percent over the past decade within the nursing profession, particularly in leadership roles. These findings align with those reported by Abd Elmoaty (2022), who explained that about two thirds of study's participant were male nurses, and same was reported by, Hajihosseini.et al (2022); Putra, Andayani and Ningrum (2021) all identified that majority of their study participants was male. However, this result was contradicted to Oppenheimer, (2021) results which reflected that the majority of the study participants were female.

Regarding to level of education, the study demonstrated that more than half of nurse managers had a Bachelor degree of nursing, this finding aligns with findings of previous research conducted by Chegini et al., (2020) who observed that a significant proportion of nurse managers held a Bachelor's degree in Nursing. As for work related characteristics of nurse managers, the study found that more than half of the nurse managers had from five to less than ten years' experience in managerial position. Consistent with this finding Elkholy, Elshall & Higazee (2020) reported that the majority of the study participants between five to ten years of experience. The present study's findings indicated that approximately two-thirds of the participants were charge nurses, defined as team leaders responsible for daily shift responsibilities and staff coordination's. While, half of participants had less than 10 years' experience in managerial position, demonstrating sufficient experience to effectively navigate workplace challenges. Indeed, that might reflect the pressing need for more advanced and contemporary management tools to align with the evolving demands of leadership, emphasizing the use of coaching and interpersonal skills. The total study sample comprised permanent employment shifts, and majority of nurse managers were employed in inpatients unites.

The present study was hypothesized that after implementation of the coaching program, there will be a difference in nurse managers mean score of interpersonal skills compared to preprogram. The results indicated a statistically significant difference in mean scores of nurse managers regarding all dimensions of interpersonal skills (communication skills, human relation skills and analytical skills) during different periods of assessment, the mean scores increased immediately post-program compared to preprogram with relative increase after three months. As demonstrated by the comparison of the total mean scores of interpersonal skills during different periods, an increase was identified between the pre- and immediate post-measures, as well as between the pre- and follow-up measures, and between the immediate post- and follow-up measures. This enhancement could be attributed to, the nurse managers' heightened awareness and recognition of the

significance of implementing coaching skills in management, that was reflected on their commitment during the training course, as well as the hospital leadership appreciation for the value and impact of coaching.

This finding aligns with the conclusions of a study by Saad (2022), who determined using observational study that coaching fosters the development of interpersonal skills across all dimensions of workplace environments. Additionally, these results were in agreement with study results by Douglas & Macphersen (2021), which revealed that interpersonal skills were positively affected by nurse managers' coaching support and that directly affects manager's updated approaches while treating their staff, through "effective listening, questioning, feedback, and managing conflicts" Their study identified coaching as a tool for facilitating learning and development and the application of new skills.

The current study findings were examined through analysis of each stage of the CLEAR Coaching Model to develop a thorough observation of each coach's experience during rehearsal and execution phase and address each coaching skill in order to answer the primary research question. The analysis revealed, a statistically significant difference of nurse' managers **total coaching skills** mean scores, regarding the "contract, listen and exploring dimensions", However, no statistically significant difference was observed regarding "action and review" dimensions, this discrepancy in "contract, listen and exploring" may be attributed to the novel concepts inherent in the coaching skills which consumes time to be fully grasped and necessitate additional training to master, and that was observable in the difference between rehearsal and execution phases. This result is consistent with the results reported by Gettman et al., (2019) who found that managers and staff nurses, who served as coaches exhibited an interpersonal relationship and reached a consensus on the contract phase of coaching which included goals and actions as part of their coaching relationship. This contract serves to guarantees that the manager and staff nurses jointly establish the objectives, strategies, relationship, and confidence for the coaching relationship.

The current results align with those of Ali El-Housary, et al (2021) who found that more than half of nurse managers participating in their coaching program exhibited low levels of overall active listening skills prior to the program. However, post program majority of participants demonstrated an increased attention and listen to verbal and non-verbal message, tone of voice, posture and gesture aimed to better understand others. A similar study was conducted by Kamara (2022) concluded that the objective of coaching is to assist staff in exploring their connections with others and themselves and mentioned that skilled coach can facilitate staff's discovery of underlying beliefs related to these concepts by employing **probing questions**, mirroring, summarizing and reflecting back thereby helping staff overcome these concepts and effect change.

In the context of nurse managers' coaching knowledge, a statistically significant difference in mean scores was identified with a notable enhancement between the pre-test and post-test knowledge. This discrepancy may be attributed to that the participants had not previously attended any coaching skills courses prior to the coaching program, and for the utilization of diverse teaching methodologies, which promote interaction and

allocate sufficient time for rehearsals and demonstrations of various coaching skills. These factors may have accelerated the improvement and retention of coaching knowledge, particularly in the context of the "conversion of knowledge to practice." Furthermore, the participants' interest in the program content was piqued by the presence of numerous real-work situational examples, ideas, and challenges. This advanced and novel strategy of coaching stimulated managers interest and participation in the learning process, self-directed learning, reasoning skills, and learning in context. Additionally, coaching rehearsal sessions emerged as an effective method for enhancing knowledge acquisition and retention. The current study's findings align with those of Ali EL-Housary et al. (2021) who reported that most study nurse managers exhibited inadequate knowledge of total coaching skills prior to the program, contrasting with their post-program knowledge levels. However, a study by Petit dit Dariel & Cristofalo (2020), yielded contradictory results, suggesting that the implementation of the training program did not significantly enhance staff knowledge.

With regard to the personal characteristics of the staff nurses, the results of the present study indicated that more than half of the participants were male nurses, which is consistent with the findings of Hajihosseini et al. (2022); Putra, Andayani, & Ningrum (2021). These studies revealed that the majority of the participants were male. However, this finding was at odds with the conclusions of Oppenheimer (2021), who determined that the predominant demographic among nurse managers in their study was female. With respect to the age of the participants, the range was from twenty-five to less than thirty years old, aligning with the findings of Ponce, et al. (2018). They reported that the majority of staff nurses in their study fell within the twenty-to-twenty-four age bracket. Furthermore, the data indicates that more than half of the participants had obtained a Bachelor of Science in Nursing.

With regard to the work-related characteristics of the staff nurses, it was observed that a majority of the participants had less than five years of experience in the organization. Furthermore, it was noted that more than one-third of the participants had between five and less than ten years of experience in nursing. these findings could be consistent with Egyptian private health organization major direction to employ young nurses with higher professional standards, required to perform the substantial nursing duties and responsibilities that demand both physical and technological abilities. The majority of the study's participants were employed in inpatient units with permanent contracts.

Concerning nurses' motivation levels, the current study identified statistically significant increases in mean scores across all dimensions of perceived motivation (individual support and communication, team spirit and collaboration, and recognition and reward) during different periods of assessment. The observed improvements could be attributed to the managers' application of coaching sessions for nurses, as well as the enhancement of interpersonal skills among nurse managers and nurses. These enhancements, in turn, had a positive impact on the nurses' perception of motivation levels and their sense of support, collaboration, recognition, and reward from senior management. This assertion is corroborated by Alexander (2016), Gift & Obindah (2020). and Whitmore (2017), all

posit that coaching constitutes a structured dialogue, wherein the coach meticulously crafts the conversation with deliberate intent, employing a range of questions and feedback which drives staff nurses to start thinking, and become motivated, aware and start to make a future plan then to take an action. (Cropley, et al., 2020) also determined that each individual has unique needs, and that it is incumbent upon the managers to meet those needs to ensure the continued motivation of employees in the work environment. Consequently, coaching can facilitate the rapid acquisition of novel skills by employees, thereby enabling managers to confidently assign tasks with the assurance of superior performance.

The statistical analysis revealed no significant correlation between perceived nurses' motivation across all dimensions and the study participants' demographic characteristics "age, gender, level of education, years of experience in organization and years of experience in nursing". But there was a statistical significance difference for work status; as the highest motivation scores were reported by permanent contracted staff nurses. This finding may be attributed to the fact that the nursing staff participating in the current study were subject to the same new managerial style, which incorporated coaching and interpersonal skills. Consequently, irrespective of their age, gender, or years of experience, the nursing staff perceived a high level of motivation in nurse managers who employed coaching and interpersonal skills. The results of this study are consistent with those reported by Kumar, Mehra, Inder, & Sharma. (2016) and Jooste & Hamanib (2017) found that personal characteristics were not significantly associated with motivation levels.

The current study exhibited that there was a high statistically significant positive correlation between observed nurse manager's coaching skills and their interpersonal skills. The observed outcomes may be attributed to the comprehensive and extensive training and rehearsals in addition to the encouragement from hospital leadership for nurse managers to adopt a different management style. This motivation led to the clarification and practical application of the taught skills, which directly influenced the nurse managers' interpersonal skills and the positive results evident in the study. These results were consistent with the findings of Hagen and Williams (2019), who explored how managerial coaching impacted interpersonal relationships in the workplace. The respondents acknowledged that managers needed to be more skilled in coaching and be able to motivate others. While these results were incongruent with the finding of cummings et al. (2018) who found coaching had a negative effect, and mentioned that staff members who have never been exposed to this kind of training as coaching and interpersonal skill might find one-on-one coaching sessions to be demanding. Notably, this study is among the few that have documented both an unsatisfactory coaching experience and a negative impact on job-related interpersonal relations among participants.

The findings of the current study were consistent with those of related studies; for instance, Kabeel (2016) research indicated that coaching in management scenarios offers an innovative perspective on the role of nurse managers. (Susanto & Sawitri. 2022;

Susanto, et al., 2023a; Susanto, et al. 2023b.) concluded in their studies that implementation of a coaching program has been shown to have a substantial positive impact on managerial performance, employee engagement, and motivation. Furthermore, Hsu et al. (2019) and Novitasari (2021) concluded that coaching is a significant intervention that affects the motivation and mindset of staff members.

In contrast, the current study yielded uniformly positive outcomes, accompanied by a statistically significant enhancement in the coaching skills of nurse managers at the post-program assessment and follow-up. Similarly, there was a notable increase in the mean scores of nurse managers' interpersonal skills immediately after the program and at the three-month follow-up assessment. Concurrently, there was an increase in the perceived motivation of staff nurses. This finding suggests that the CLEAR coaching model, which emphasizes Contract, Listening, Exploring, Action, and Review, has a positive effect on nurse managers' interpersonal skills, including communication, human relations and analytical skills, which in turn positively impacts perceived staff nurses' motivation.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study, all the study hypotheses were supported, as there was statistically significant increase in interpersonal skills mean scores among nurse managers compared to pre coaching program combined with a high mean score of nurses' motivation compared to pre coaching program. Additionally, the third hypothesis was also positively supported as there was statistically significant increase among nurse managers coaching knowledge test scores compared to preprogram.

Indeed, the coaching program effect was noticeable improving nurse managers both coaching skills regarding to application of “contract, listen, exploring, action and review”, interpersonal skills using “communication skills, human relation skills, and analytical skills” Also, for staff nurses' motivation level regarding perceived “individual support & communication, team spirit & collaboration and recognition & reward”.

Inclusive, this quasi-experimental study increases the understanding of the relationship between investing on nurse manager's coaching training “which became one of the most updated and innovative management style”, and the nurse managers positive change toward utilization of best interpersonal skills improving nurses' motivation.

Limitations and suggestions for future research

The presented study was carried out using observational checklist and questionnaire survey, which considered an effective way of collecting data, and showing the effect, but the quantitative nature of the questionnaire method did not cover the qualitative part of the nurse managers characteristics change in depth and as such, was limited to the interpretation of participants changes regarding interpersonal skills and motivation level, which considered to be as limit of this study. Therefore, in the future, considering the implementation of a qualitative survey or carrying out a survey at several health care setting and comparing the findings regarding the issue in hypotheses is highly recommended.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Formal approval and permission to conduct the research were diligently obtained from the Scientific Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Nursing Cairo University, Egypt. (ID number/20210507). Furthermore, before any participation in the study, written informed consent was obtained from nurse managers and nursing staff who were voluntarily agreed to participate in the research.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Availability of data and material

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published Article. Any additional data could be available upon request from the corresponding author.

Competing of interest

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose

Funding

Not applicable

Author's contributions

Fatma Essam: Conceptualization, methodology, data collection, statistical analysis, prepared figures, data curation, investigation, original draft, writing review & editing of the manuscript. Nehad E. Fekry: & Sahar Hassan: Visualization, and Supervision, all authors have reviewed and agreed to the content of this manuscript.

Clinical trials number: not applicable.

Acknowledgements

We sincerely thank the hospital director and the nurse managers and supervisors of all the clinical units for their incredible support and cooperation. Also, we would like to extend our appreciation to the nurses who are actively participated in this study, as their contribution was crucial in enabling us to complete this research.

References

- 1) Abd Elmoaty, A. E. E. (2022). Organizational Justice: An Educational Program for Nurses' Leaders to Enhance the Creativity of their Staff Nurses at Work. *Helwan International Journal for Nursing Research and Practice*, 1(1), 1-13.
- 2) Alexander, G. (2016). *Excellence in coaching: The industry guide* (3rd ed.). Kogan Page.
- 3) Ali EL-Housary, N. M., Shabaan, F. M., EL-Demerdash, S. M., & Shokier, M. E. (2021). Effect of Educational Program on Head Nurses' Coaching Skills to Manage Novice Nurses Role Ambiguity. *Tanta Scientific Nursing Journal*, 21(2), 143-170.
- 4) Al-Yami, M., Galdas, P., & Watson, R. (2018). Leadership style and organizational commitment among nursing staff in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of nursing management*, 26(5), 531-539.
- 5) Backman, A., Ahnlund, P., Sjögren, K., Lövheim, H., McGilton, K. S., & Edvardsson, D. (2020). Embodying person-centered being and doing: Leading towards person-centered care in nursing homes as narrated by managers. *Journal of clinical nursing*, 29(1-2), 172-183. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.15075>.

- 6) Beenen, G., Pichler, S., & Davoudpour, S. (2018). Interpersonal skills in MBA admissions: How are they conceptualized and assessed? *Journal of Management Education*, 42(1), 34-54.
- 7) Blanton, J.S. & Wasylyshyn, K.M. (2018). Beyond the client/coach dyad in coaching senior business leaders. *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 70(4), 339–350.
- 8) Blessing White. (2009). *The Coaching Conundrum: Building a Coaching Culture that Drives Organizational Success*. Princetown, NJ.
- 9) Bozer, G., & Delegach, M. (2019). Bringing context to workplace coaching: A theoretical framework based on uncertainty avoidance and regulatory focus. *Human Resource Development Review*, 18(3), 376–402.
- 10) Burrows K. (2018). *Coaching skills ultimate guide coaching techniques. Coaching skills-tips. Making Business Matter. Trainers to the UK Grocery Industry*. Available at: www.makingbusinessmatter.co.uk.
- 11) Chegini, Z., Kakemam, E., Asghari Jafarabadi, M., & Janati, A. (2020). The impact of patient safety culture and the leader coaching behavior of nurses on the intention to report errors: a cross-sectional survey. *BMC nursing*, 19, 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-020-00472-4>.
- 12) Copley, M., Heron, R. M., Simonds, L. P. & Steiner, S., (2020). Reasons for Staying with your Employer. Identifying the Key Organizational Predictors of Employee Retention within a Global Energy Business. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, Issue January.
- 13) Cummings, G. G., Hewko, S. J., Wang, M., Wong, C. A., Laschinger, H. K. S., & Estabrooks, C. A. (2018). Impact of managers' coaching conversations on staff knowledge use and performance in long-term care settings. *Worldviews Evidence Based Nursing*, 15(1), 62– 71. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12233>.
- 14) De Haan, E., Duckworth, A., Birch, D., & Jones, C., (2013). Executive coaching outcome research: The contribution of common factors such as relationship, personality match, and self-efficacy. *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 65(1), 40.
- 15) de Haan, E., Grant, A. M., Burger, Y., & Eriksson, P. O. (2016). A large-scale study of executive and workplace coaching: The relative contributions of relationship, personality match, and self-efficacy. *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 68(3), 189.
- 16) Douglas, N. F., & MacPherson, M. K. (2021). Positive changes in certified nursing assistants' communication behaviors with people with dementia: Feasibility of a coaching strategy. *American Journal of Speech-Language Pathology*, 30(1), 239–252. https://doi.org/10.1044/2020_AJSLP-20-00065.
- 17) Elkholy, S. M., Elshall, S. E., & Higazee, M. Z. A. (2020). Organizational justice: a predictor of job satisfaction among hospital nurses. *International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing*. Vol. (7) 2, p: 384-392
- 18) Ellinger, A. D., Jones, J., Hamlin, R. G., & Beattie, R. S. (2023). The manager as coach. *The complete handbook of coaching*, 263-280.
- 19) Gettman, H. J., Edinger, S. K., & Wouters, K. (2019). Assessing contracting and the coaching relationship: Necessary infrastructure? *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring*, 17(1), 46-62. <https://doi.org/10.24384/Onfx-0779>.
- 20) Gift, R. A. A., & Obindah, F. (2020). Examining the influence of motivation on organizational productivity in Bayelsa state private hospitals. *Open Access Journal of Science*, 4(3), 94-108.
- 21) Hagen S, M., & Williams E, D. (2019). The Impact of Loyalty and Self-Determination on Managerial Coaching Outcomes. *Performance Improvement Quarterly*, 32(3), 207-236.

- 22) Hajihosseini, F., Mousazadeh, N., Nazari, R., & Nia, H. S. (2022). What parts of “incident reporting culture” can predict nurses' willingness to report errors? *Research Square*,1(1),1-10 <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2328596/v1>.
- 23) Hastings, L.J. and Kane, C., (2018). Distinguishing mentoring, coaching, and advising for leadership development. *New directions for student leadership*, (158), pp.9-22
- 24) Hawkins, P., & Smith, N. (2013). *Coaching, mentoring and organizational consultancy: Supervision, skills and development: Vol. second edition*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- 25) Hsu, Y.P., Chun-Yang, P., Pi-Hui, T. & Ching-Wei, T. (2019), “Managerial coaching, job performance, and team commitment: the meditating effect of psychological capital”, *Advances in Management and Applied Economics*, Vol. 9 No. 5, pp. 101-125.
- 26) International Coaching Federation (2020). *Global Coaching Study*. Available at: <https://coachingfederation.org/research/global-coaching-study>. Google Scholar.
- 27) Jooste, K., & Hamani, M. (2017). The motivational needs of primary health care nurses to acquire power as leaders in a mine clinic setting. *Health SA Gesondheid*. 22(1), 43-51 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hsag.2016.09.005>.
- 28) Kabeel, A. (2016). Impact of Coaching Program on Nurse Manages' Awareness Regarding Coaching Leadership. *Med. J. Cairo University*, 84(1), 1481-1487.
- 29) Kalkavan, S., & Katrinli, A. (2014). The effects of managerial coaching behaviors on the employees' perception of job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and job performance: Case study on insurance industry in Turkey. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 150, 1137-1147.
- 30) Kamara, R. I. (2022). *Executive coaching and Leadership: The impact executive coaching has on leadership in Telefonica* (Doctoral dissertation, Dublin, National College of Ireland).
- 31) King, I.M. (1971). *Toward a theory for nursing: General concepts of human behavior*. New York: Wiley.
- 32) Kumar, P., Mehra, A., Inder, D., & Sharma, N. (2016). Organizational commitment and intrinsic motivation of regular and contractual primary health care providers. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*, 5(1), 94-100.
- 33) Lawrence, P. (2017). Managerial coaching-a literature review. *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring*, 15(2), 43. CrossRef Full Text | Google Scholar.
- 34) Lundin, K., Silén, M., Strömberg, A., Engström, M., & Skytt, B. (2022). Staff structural empowerment—Observations of first-line managers and interviews with managers and staff. *Journal of nursing management*, 30(2), 403-412. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.13513>
- 35) McCarthy, G., & Milner, J. (2013). Managerial coaching: challenges, opportunities and training. *Journal of Management Development*, 32(7), 768-779.
- 36) McCarthy, G. & Milner, J. (2020), “Ability, motivation and opportunity: managerial coaching in practice”, *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*, Vol. 58 No. 1, 149-170.
- 37) McLean, G. N., Yang, B., Kuo, M. H. C., Tolbert, A. S., & Larkin, C. (2005). Development and initial validation of an instrument measuring managerial coaching skill. *Human resource development quarterly*, 16(2), 157-178.
- 38) MacLennan, N. (2017). *Coaching and mentoring*. Routledge.
- 39) Marquis, B. and Huston, C. & Jones, G. (2018). *Contemporary management. Motivation and performance*. Global Ed, McGraw-Hill-Irwin, 6th ed., p, 76

- 40) Matteson, M. L., Ming, Y., & Silva, D. E. (2021). The relationship between work conditions and perceptions of organizational justice among library employees. *Library & Information Science Research*, 43(2), 101093. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lisr.2021.101093>.
- 41) Mear, F., & Werner, R. A. (2020). Subsidiarity as secret of success: "Hidden Champion" SMEs and subsidiarity as winning HRM configuration in interdisciplinary case studies. *Employee Relations: The International Journal*, 43(2), 524–554. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ER-03-2020-0141>.
- 42) Novitasari, D. (2021), "The role of managerial coaching on performance: mediating analysis of employee psychological capital", *International Journal of Social and Management Studies*, Vol. 2 No. 3, pp. 70-83.
- 43) Oppenheimer, T. H. (2021). 4 steps to becoming a nurse manager, retrieved from <https://nurse.org/resources/nurse-manager/>
- 44) Petit Dit Dariel, O., & Cristofalo, P. (2020). Improving patient safety in two French hospitals: why teamwork training is not enough. *Journal of Health Organization and Management*, 34(6), 639-653.
- 45) Ponce, C. V., Llorin, A. L. P., & Cordial, C. B. (2018). ENN-RICH:(Engaging Novice Nurses Through Reflecting and Interactive Coaching Huddle). *Journal of Nursing & Healthcare*, 3(3), 1-12.
- 46) Putra, K. R., Andayani, T., & Ningrum, E. H. (2021). Job satisfaction and caring behavior among nurses in a military hospital: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of public health research*, 10(2), jphr-2021.
- 47) Rios, J. A., Ling, G., Pugh, R., Becker, D., and Bacall, A. (2020). Identifying critical 21st-century skills for workplace success: a content analysis of job advertisements. *Educ. Res.* 49, 80–89.
- 48) Rothwell, W. J., & Bakhshandeh, B. (2022). *High-Performance Coaching for Managers: A Step-By-Step Approach to Increase Employees' Performance and Productivity*. Productivity Press.
- 49) Saad, H. K. (2022). Coaching impact on employees and organizational performance in the middle east healthcare industry. *Journal of Advanced Research in Leadership*, 1(1), 1-12.
- 50) Siedlecki, S. L. (2020). Quasi-experimental research designs. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*, 34(5), 198-202.
- 51) Susanto, P. C., Sawitri, N. N., Ali, H., Suroso, S., & Sastrodiharjo, I. (2023a). Performance Management as a Mediation of Variable of Competence and Coaching Skills That Impacts Organization Sustainability. *Formosa Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, (FJMR), 2(4), 719–728.
- 52) Susanto, P. C., Sawitri, N. N., Suroso, S., & Rony, Z. T. (2023b). Human Resource Business Partners: Recruitment, Coaching, and Leadership Development. *International Journal of Integrative Sciences*, 2(4), 457–482. <https://doi.org/10.55927/ijis.v2i4.3680>.
- 53) Susanto, P. C., & Sawitri, N. N. (2022). Coaching, mentoring, leadership transformation and employee engagement: A review of the literature. *Dinasti International Journal of Education Management and Social Science*, 4(2), 297-308.
- 54) Westcott L. (2016); How coaching can play a key role in the development of nurse managers. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*. 25(17-18): 2669-77.
- 55) Whitmore, J. (2017). *Coaching for Performance: The Principles and Practice of Coaching and Leadership*, (5th ed) Boston, Massachusetts.
- 56) Yamane, T. (1967). *Statistics, An Introductory Analysis* (2nd ed.). New York: Harper and Row.
- 57) Yang, Y., & Liu, H. (2021). The effect of patient safety culture on nurses' near-miss reporting intention: The moderating role of perceived severity of near misses. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 26(2), 6-16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987120979344>.